

Advanced Semantic Integration with RDF and R2RML for Unified Data Management

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Abstract. Due to the growing demand for data integration in different fields, it has led to the development of innovative methods for the semantic integration of heterogeneous data sources. This study proposes a new approach that uses the Resource Description Framework (RDF) and Relational Database (RDB) in the RDB to RDF Mapping Language (R2RML) for the semantic integration of data resources within the framework of an integrated semantic model. This approach consists of an Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL) pipeline connected to an RDF triple store that allows the use of multiple ontologies in different domains and the management of distinct data models. The applicability of this method was demonstrated in the fields of healthcare and the Internet of Things, enhancing a unified view of data and interoperability. This process involves converting the data to RDF, creating an integrated RDF specification, storing it in an RDF repository, and querying it through a SPARQL endpoint, enabling intelligent decision-making processes. The implementation and results of this method show the integrity of semantic data and its strength in addressing the complex requirements of semantic interaction in multi-domain environments. This research promotes the applicability of semantic technologies for integrated data management by integrating a comprehensive set of tools and proving its practical applications. The proposed innovative approach provides a promising solution for the semantic integration of heterogeneous data sources, improving interoperability and enabling intelligent decision-making processes.

Keywords: Semantic Integration · RDF · R2RML · Data Interoperability.

1 Introduction

Semantic Web technologies, such as Resource Description Framework (RDF) and Relational Database (RDB) to RDF Mapping Language (R2RML), have played a role in advancing data engineering and management across sectors like healthcare, Internet of Things (IoT), environmental monitoring and social services. These tools help in organizing and exchanging information, effectively promoting communication between systems—an essential aspect for smooth data sharing and integration [1]. In the healthcare sector, Semantic Web technologies assist in creating templates to adhere to study metadata standards, establishing a robust framework for practical semantic interoperability [2].

Using RDF enables the capture of information content that goes beyond syntax, facilitating reasoning and transformative methods crucial for integrating data and ensuring interoperability [3]. Additionally, Semantic Web tools have been utilized in healthcare data integration and analysis efforts, creating possibilities for cross-domain collaboration and enhancing patient care as well as clinical research results [4]. In the context of the IoT, Semantic Web technologies act as a foundational element for interoperability across different formats, protocols, and platforms, providing a unified view of heterogeneous devices and services [5]. In addition, these technologies enable Semantic Web data visualization, which is critical for analyzing and understanding complex data sets [6].

RDF and Semantic Web technologies have been used to facilitate meaningful data communication between clinicians and patients in heterogeneous healthcare IoT infrastructures. Semantic interoperability is the term used to describe this process [7]. In addition, the collaboration between the Semantic Web and the IoT has improved the analysis and representation of sensor data, thereby increasing the integration, discovery, and analysis of data in various applications, including smart cities and home automation. The efficacy of RDF in improving data sharing within the healthcare sector has been recognized, particularly for its role in managing spatial and spatiotemporal data on the internet and various applications, yet challenges remain in scaling these solutions to accommodate the vast diversity of healthcare data standards and protocols [8]. This aligns with the broader need for enhanced interoperability in healthcare, which suggests that despite ongoing efforts, current methodologies may not fully address the complexities of healthcare data integration [9].

The study presented an innovative approach using Semantic Web technologies for IoT applications, emphasizing the improvement in device communication and data aggregation [6]. The approach introduces several key advancements:

- Centralized Semantic Layer: Employing a centralized semantic layer abstracts the complexity of individual system mappings and promotes a scalable infrastructure that can incorporate new data sources without extensive reconfiguration.

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- Enhanced Interoperability: The proposed method leverages RDF and R2RML to create a unified semantic framework that enables seamless data integration across diverse domains such as healthcare and IoT.
- Semantic Enrichment: The use of multiple ontologies and high-level transformation specifications (RML) introduces a rich semantic layer that enhances the context and meaning of data, facilitating more intelligent decision-making processes.
- Scalability and Flexibility: The approach supports the dynamic integration of data from various sources, ensuring that the semantic framework remains current, accurate, and flexible.

While this work marks significant progress, it also brings gaps in creating a truly unified data model capable of encompassing the heterogeneity inherent in IoT devices and platforms. This gap underscores the motivation behind seeking a more robust solution for unified data management in the IoT landscape [10].

Research on environmental monitoring using Semantic Web tools showcased the advantages of semantic technologies in facilitating data analysis and visualization, particularly in the context of sensor networks for environmental decision support applications [11]. However, the study also underlines the challenges in integrating data from disparate sources, especially when dealing with non-anonymous datasets, thus highlighting the importance of addressing varied data types in semantic integration efforts [12]. Despite these advancements, a common theme across recent literature is the challenge of achieving a comprehensive solution that can handle the multifaceted requirements of semantic interoperability, especially in multi-domain contexts. These studies, while pioneering, often fall short in offering a scalable, all-encompassing framework that can address the nuances of different data domains, from healthcare to IoT and beyond.

In response to these challenges, the proposed method introduces an innovative RDF-based process for semantic interoperability that leverages existing RDF tools to create an ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) pipeline connected to an RDF triplestore. ETL is an acronym for "extract, transform, load," which refers to the three interconnected processes involved in data integration, including extracting data from one database and then transforming and loading it into another database. This approach enables the use of multiple ontologies from different domains and can manage various data models, thereby presenting a significant advancement over the limitations highlighted in current literature. By incorporating high-level transformation specifications (RML), the proposed methodology introduces semantics in data, enabling aggregation from diverse sources and providing a unified model and a single view of all data. This innovation marks a pivotal step forward in addressing the pressing need for improved interoperability and data management across varied sectors, effectively bridging the gaps identified in existing research.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews the background knowledge necessary for understanding the proposed approach, focusing on semantic data models and ontologies. Section 3 details the proposed methodology and its general structure. Section 4 evaluates the method, discusses the

results, and shares insights from the study. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper and suggests directions for future research.

2 Background

2.1 Semantic Data Model

Semantic data models help us understand and show how different pieces of data relate to each other. They look at both how data is organized and what it means. These models use ontology principles, which means they accurately show knowledge for a specific area. They explain what things (entities) are, their features, and how they connect. This method is better than traditional ways because it puts real meaning into the data. This lets computers think about data more like humans do. The models use things like the RDF and RDF Schema (RDFS), as well as ideas from Tim Berners-Lee, to make sharing and connecting information on the Web easier [13].

In a world where data ecosystems are continuously developing, semantic data models address the main challenges in data collaboration and integration in diverse sectors such as health, IoT, and the environment. By implementing an integrated semantic process, it is possible to coordinately collect and analyze data from different sources and formats, which leads to a more accurate and comprehensive understanding of complex data. In health, for example, these models can align data from electronic health records, genetic databases, and clinical studies, thereby facilitating advanced research and personalized medicine. Similarly, in the field of the Internet of Things, these models allow data from various sensors and devices to be used seamlessly, creating a coordinated system for smart cities and various industries. The flexibility and expressiveness of these models make them effective tools for dealing with the complexities of data management in the modern era and provide new fields for innovations and new insights in many fields.

2.2 Ontology

In Semantic Web and data science, ontologies are key. They help organize information by laying out a clear structure of concepts and their connections. This setup lets both people and systems understand and use data consistently, improving how different data systems work together [14].

Ontologies outline what data means in a way machines can understand, making it easier to combine data, ask questions, and analyze information. They even help discover new insights from existing data. With ontologies, applications can do more than show data; they can understand and act on it. This supports advanced options like smart searching and linking different data sources [15]. Developing and using ontologies is crucial for the Semantic Web's goal: to make data from anywhere connectable and usable by both machines and people in a clear and meaningful way.

Fig. 1 shows how medical information is connected in an easy-to-understand way. This ontology defines the relationships between a patient, their medical

build detailed data models with RDF Schema (RDFS) and the Web Ontology Language (OWL), adding deeper meaning to data. RDF is crucial for linking data while keeping its meaning, which is important for sharing and analyzing data. This makes RDF a main tool for systems that handle knowledge and reasoning on the web, in healthcare, environmental tracking, and more [16].

Fig. 2. Structure of an RDF Triple: Subject, Predicate, Object

Fig. 2 presents a graphical illustration of an RDF triple, the building block of the RDF. In this model, the 'Subject' represents the resource from which information is being described, the 'Predicate' denotes the type of relation or attribute that connects the subject to the 'Object', which is the value or another resource linked to the subject. This simple yet powerful structure enables the RDF to encode the interconnected relationships between data points, encapsulating not just the data but also the semantics—the meanings—behind the data.

Each RDF triple can be thought of as a statement of "fact" that collectively forms a web of interconnected data points, known as an RDF graph. These graphs are fundamental to the Semantic Web, allowing for data from disparate sources to be combined in a meaningful way. Through this linkage, RDF facilitates a consistent format for data exchange and a method for integrating diverse information in a queryable and machine-understandable format, enhancing the capability of intelligent data analysis and interpretation across various domains.

3 Method

This paper introduces an innovative methodology for semantic data integration that leverages the principles of the Unified Semantics Model. The left side of Fig. 3 illustrates the traditional approach where systems A, B, C, D, and E are interconnected in a complex and often convoluted manner. This arrangement typically leads to redundant mappings, increased maintenance costs, and a higher likelihood of inconsistencies due to the pairwise integration between systems.

Transitioning from the complex model, the proposed methodology adopts a "Unified Semantics Model" approach, as shown on the right side of Fig. 3. Here, a centralized semantic layer, represented by the blue square, serves as an intermediary that abstracts the complexity of individual system mappings. Each system interfaces with this semantic layer using a standardized interface,

Fig. 3. Comparative Diagram of System Integration Models: Complex System Interconnectivity vs. Unified Semantics Model

designed to interpret and translate the data into a unified semantic framework. This centralized approach simplifies the architecture by reducing direct connections, thereby streamlining data integration and promoting more robust data management practices. The semantic layer employs an RDF-based framework that harnesses the RDF and R2RML (RDB to RDF Mapping Language) for defining and storing data. It effectively orchestrates the translation of data between heterogeneous systems, ensuring that information from systems A through E can be aggregated and queried as if it were a single, homogeneous dataset. This not only enhances interoperability among the systems but also provides a scalable infrastructure capable of incorporating new data sources without the need for extensive reconfiguration.

Fig. 4 illustrates the whole structure of the proposed Unified Semantics Model, which encompasses the comprehensive approach for integrating semantic data described in the research. This paradigm demonstrates a complex process that starts with various data sources at the foundation. These sources encompass multi-domain systems that offer healthcare data, IoT data, and other types of data. The data undergoes a 'lifting' process, in which wrappers, following the W3C R2RML specification, semantically change the data and translate it into an RDF-compatible format.

The essential component of this architecture is the 'Unified Semantics' layer. In this context, the process of reasoning and comprehension is enhanced by utilizing established guidelines and conceptual frameworks like the Unified Code for Units of Measure (UCUM) [17], the Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine (SNOMED), the Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator (SOSA), and Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) [18], which enhance the semantic

Fig. 4. Overview of the Unified Semantics Integration Architecture

accuracy and richness of the data. The improved data is subsequently inputted into the Common RDF Store, which functions as a centralized repository of information. This enables the execution of intricate queries and retrieval of knowledge using SPARQL, the query language for RDF.

The final outcome of this approach is the capability to carry out complex data analysis while preserving the accuracy of both syntax and semantics. The system guarantees the consistency and semantic enrichment of data by extracting information, including its context and meaning, throughout exchanges. The suggested method is innovative in creating fully interoperable systems in healthcare and other fields. It enables the smooth integration and interpretation of large and diverse collections of data. This method is used to solve the problems associated with traditional data integration methods. It makes it easy to acquire data from many sources and organize it into a cohesive framework, making it more valuable for analytical and decision-making processes.

Fig. 5, illustrates the sequential steps in the proposed Unified Semantics Model, detailing the transition from data source to semantic enrichment and query processing. The process commences with data models from Systems A and B, each being 'lifted' to an RDF format via R2RML mapping, signifying

Fig. 7. Conversion Workflow from Relational Databases to RDF Triples Using R2RML

The output of this process is a structured RDF graph, as exemplified in Fig. 7. The graph demonstrates the RDF triple pattern, where relational data now takes the form of semantic statements. These triples allow machines to process and interpret data, not just at the syntactic level, but with an understanding of the relationships and properties defined within the RDF schema and its associated vocabularies. For instance, the RDF representation of environmental readings can denote not only the values of humidity or temperature but also their contextual relevance to specific users or locations, as defined in the ontology. The final stage of this transformation is the refinement of these RDF graphs. For practical illustration, the code snippet in Fig. 8 demonstrates a segment of R2RML mapping, translating JSON data structures to RDF. This snippet provides a window into how machines can process the information at a semantic level, paving the way for enhanced data interpretation and utilization across diverse domains.

3.2 Unified RDF Specification

Following the transformation of data from relational databases to RDF, the next phase in the proposed methodology involves the creation of a Unified RDF Specification. This step ensures that the diverse data sources, now in RDF format, conform to a consistent and harmonized schema which facilitates seamless interoperability between different systems and domains.

In Fig. 9, the RDF enrichment phase is initiated by incorporating a suite of recognized standards and ontologies. These integrations are pivotal in sculpting a resilient semantic architecture that can adeptly mirror the intricate nature of healthcare details, measurement specifics, and IoT data interconnectivity. The FHIR standard streamlines healthcare data exchange, enhancing clarity and compatibility across systems, while the UCUM ensures precise representation of measurements, critical in both healthcare and scientific contexts. Meanwhile, the SOSA framework, as part of the Semantic Sensor Network ontology, structures observations and actions in the physical world, enabling seamless integration of IoT and device data. Schema.org’s collection of schemas for structured data on the internet boosts the visibility and usability of data, ensuring it is accessible and actionable across various web platforms. Each of these components contributes to the establishment of a shared semantic vocabulary, facilitating

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1 @prefix rml: <http://semweb.mmlab.be/ns/rml#>.
2 @prefix rr: <http://batlab.w3.org/ns/r2rml#>.
3 @prefix ql: <http://semweb.mmlab.be/ns/ql#>.
4 @prefix xsd: <http://batlab.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>.
5 @prefix ex: <http://example.com/ns#>.
6 @prefix : <http://example.org/rules/>.
7
8 :UserMapping a rr:TriplesMap;
9   rml:logicalSource [
10     rml:source "./data.json";
11     rml:referenceFormulation ql:JSONPath;
12     rml:iterator "$.Users[*]"
13   ];
14   rr:subjectMap [
15     rr:template "http://example.com/user/{userid}";
16     rr:class ex:User
17   ];
18   rr:predicateObjectMap [
19     rr:predicate ex:carer;
20     rr:objectMap [ rml:reference "carer" ]
21   ];
22   rr:predicateObjectMap [
23     rr:predicate ex:patient;
24     rr:objectMap [ rml:reference "patient" ]
25   ];
26   rr:predicateObjectMap [
27     rr:predicate ex:name;
28     rr:objectMap [ rml:reference "name" ]
29   ];
30   rr:predicateObjectMap [
31     rr:predicate ex:surname;
32     rr:objectMap [ rml:reference "surname" ]
33   ];
34   rr:predicateObjectMap [
35     rr:predicate ex:dni;
36     rr:objectMap [ rml:reference "dni" ]
37   ];
38   rr:predicateObjectMap [
39     rr:predicate ex:token;
40     rr:objectMap [ rml:reference "token" ]
41   ].

```

Fig. 8. Sample R2RML Mapping Configuration for JSON to RDF Conversion Refinement

a more integrated and meaningful interpretation of data drawn from diverse sources.

As a sample, Fig. 10 shows the Unified RDF Specification necessitates pinpointing and synchronizing pivotal elements found within various data sets. This phase involves unifying crucial data entities, such as user and patient details, alongside IoT devices and environmental event data, by employing common vocabularies to foster a cohesive model. The SOSA/SSN ontologies offer terminologies essential for IoT data related to sensors and observations, whereas Schema.org provides the necessary vocabularies for making web data structured and machine-readable. Concurrently, FHIR is utilized for specifying healthcare information, guaranteeing that the data aligns seamlessly with the established healthcare system frameworks.

The completion of this process is the definition of mappings for the Unified RDF, where the RDF Mapping Language (RML) specification is updated to include mappings that cover both healthcare and IoT data sources. This specification acts as the blueprint for transforming and unifying the data, encapsulating

```

10 <http://example.com/ontology/environment/humidity/Disp1> a sosa:Observation;
11   example:belongsToUser <http://example.com/ontology/user/User1>;
12   sosa:hasSimpleResult "45"^^ucum:percent;
13   sosa:observedProperty sosa:Property_Humidity;
14   sosa:resultTime "2023-01-01T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTimeStamp .
15
16 <http://example.com/ontology/environment/luminosity/Disp1> a sosa:Observation;
17   example:belongsToUser <http://example.com/ontology/user/User1>;
18   sosa:hasSimpleResult "200"^^ucum:lux;
19   sosa:observedProperty sosa:Property_Luminosity;
20   sosa:resultTime "2023-01-01T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTimeStamp .
21
22 <http://example.com/ontology/environment/temperature/Disp1> a sosa:Observation;
23   example:belongsToUser <http://example.com/ontology/user/User1>;
24   sosa:hasSimpleResult "22.5"^^ucum:degreeCelsius;
25   sosa:observedProperty sosa:Property_Temperature;
26   sosa:resultTime "2023-01-01T00:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTimeStamp .
27
28 <http://example.com/ontology/events/Disp1> a sosa:Observation;
29   sosa:hasSimpleResult true, "0"^^xsd:number;
30   sosa:observedProperty sosa:Property_Motion, sosa:Property_Occupancy;
31   sosa:resultTime "2023-01-01T12:00:00Z"^^xsd:dateTimeStamp .
32

```

Fig. 9. Integrating Standards and Ontologies into RDF Graphs for Enhanced Semantics

Fig. 10. Associating User and Device Entities with Industry Standards in Healthcare and Sensor Data Management

both the structure and semantics required for a wide range of applications. By defining these mappings, it is ensured that the RDF data is not only syntactically correct but also semantically rich and capable of supporting advanced analytics and reasoning tasks.

3.3 RDF Data Repository Storage

The next stage in the data transformation pipeline, as depicted in Fig. 11, is the storage of RDF data within a purpose-built repository optimized for high-performance data retrieval and semantic querying capabilities. This repository employs RDF Triple Storage technology, an adept system for maintaining semantic data in a structured RDF format. It allows for advanced data interrogation through SPARQL queries and is capable of inferring new knowledge from the pre-existing dataset. The intrinsic schema-less nature of this storage solution and its relationship with linked data principles greatly simplify the process of linking and cross-referencing information across varied data collections. For the implementation of the RDF triple storage, Apache Jena [19] has been chosen, a robust framework known for its powerful data handling and querying features, aligning with the needs for a scalable and flexible semantic data infrastructure.

Fig. 11. Data Transformation and Storage Flow: From RML Processing to RDF Data in Apache Jena Triple Store with SPARQL Endpoint Access

3.4 SPARQL Query Endpoint

At the heart of the integrated data framework lies the SPARQL Query Endpoint, as shown in Fig. 11. This interface is the linchpin for querying the unified semantic data, facilitating complex searches that underpin insightful analytics and informed decision-making. The endpoint acts as a conduit between users and the RDF data repository, translating intricate query requests into actionable data retrievals. With this capability, users can execute refined searches across the interconnected datasets, harnessing the full potential of the Semantic Web to extract nuanced knowledge and drive strategic initiatives.

Fig. 12. Integrating Temperature Data from Multiple Systems through ETL to RDF Mapping for Querying via SPARQL Endpoint

This study introduces an iterative refinement process essential to the adaptability and scalability of the proposed Unified Semantics Model. This process, as shown in Fig. 12, encapsulates a cyclical approach to enhancing the semantic model to ensure that it remains responsive to evolving system requirements and data structures. At the center of this process exists the Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) mechanism, which is tailored to work with semantic data using the R2RML process. The input data, obtained from various systems A and B in this instance, is first 'lifted' into a semantic context, allowing for the rich representation of relationships and properties inherent in the RDF format.

Once transformed, the semantic data is put into an RDF Triple Store, which not only acts as a repository but also serves as a semantic engine capable of discerning complex relationships within the data. This semantic richness paves the way for advanced querying capabilities through the SPARQL endpoint, which is the interface for data interrogation and insight extraction.

Crucially, this methodology does not represent a static solution but a model that upgrades on iterative improvements. As new data models appear or existing ones undergo changes, the ETL pipeline is revisited. Mappings are refined, ontologies are expanded, and the RDF schema is updated, thereby the semantic framework’s alignment with the data it represents. This iterative process not only exemplifies the proposed method’s ability to integrate and manage data dynamically but also underscores the agility of the proposed approach in embracing changes, ensuring that the integrated data remains current, accurate, and semantically relevant.

4 Result and Discussion

This study describes a detailed approach to blending different kinds of data using a unified model. The following discussion explains the practical applications of the methodology, the selection of tools underpinning the semantic data integration, and an analytical discourse on the outcomes observed from their utilization.

The ETL pipeline relies on Spring Boot [20], which simplifies the creation of server-side applications by reducing the need for extensive configuration. Spring Boot was utilized for its robust API components, including a web server, comprehensive dependency injection mechanisms, and seamless integrations with external databases and storage systems. The framework’s flexibility allows for easy adaptation as the application requirements change. For API documentation and testing, Swagger was employed. It provides a user-friendly interface for both developers and stakeholders to visualize and interact with the API’s resources without needing to implement the logic. Swagger’s testing tools also enable continuous verification of API endpoints, ensuring that changes in the backend do not break existing contracts.

Dependencies for the R2RML process were managed with Maven, which simplifies the build process for Java projects. Specifically, the Maven package for `rml.io` was leveraged, a robust tool for expressing customized R2RML mappings that convert relational databases into rich RDF graphs. For RDF triple storage, Apache Jena was incorporated, a free and open-source Java framework for building Semantic Web and Linked Data applications. The Apache Jena packages from the Maven repository provided the necessary infrastructure to interact with an external Triple Store, facilitating RDF data management and SPARQL endpoint functionality.

To visualize RDF data and execute validation queries, Neo4j [21] was used, coupled with neo-semantics (neosemantics). Neo4j offers an intuitive graph database that supports the Cypher query language, allowing for complex queries and vi-

sual representations of RDF graphs. This was particularly beneficial for understanding the intricate relationships within the data. Lastly, the RDF data store was powered by Apache Jena, chosen for its comprehensive support for RDF data management. It enables sophisticated querying capabilities, allowing for the extraction and analysis of semantic data, thus underpinning the intelligent decision-making processes advocated by the proposed method.

Fig. 13. Data Ingestion through R2RML API and Visualization of RDF Conversion

The Fig. 13 illustrates the process of data ingestion. In this process, the first step involves introducing data in JSON format to the RML mapping process. The JSON structure provided should reflect the data model of the system being investigated. This step is crucial in converting the data model into a semantic structure through the RML process. This representation is essential in understanding how the proposed methodology can accommodate various data formats and adapt them to a unified semantic form. This emphasizes the adaptability and efficiency of the proposed integration approach.

The transformation of data from JSON structures to RDF is a vital step in semantic integration, enabling data from various sources to be amalgamated into a unified information model. As depicted in Fig.14, the RML process is invoked through a user-friendly API, with Swagger facilitating the interaction. It demonstrates how data, ingested in JSON format, is methodically translated into an RDF graph using the defined RML mappings. Also, Fig.14 captures the outcome of the RDF generation API, showcasing the successful conversion of JSON data into RDF triples. The API’s response, as illustrated, provides immediate feedback in the form of a Turtle file—a compact, human-readable format for RDF data. This verifies that the semantic representation of data aligns with the specifications and underlines the efficacy of the RML process in preparing the data for subsequent semantic querying and analysis.

Fig. 14. RDF Generation from JSON Data via the RML Mapping Process

This stage focuses on the accuracy of data transformation, the ease of validating RDF output, and the seamless workflow facilitated by the integration of Swagger within the ETL pipeline. This API-driven approach underscores the streamlined process for converting and validating data as it moves from one form to a semantically enriched model, thereby supporting the overarching goal of enhancing data interoperability.

Fig. 15. Graphical Visualization of RDF Data in Neo4j Using Neosemantics

Following the conversion of the proposed method’s data model into RDF using the RML mapper, the next logical step in the proposed methodology in-

in Fig.16, presents a query field ready for information retrieval. Users can seamlessly execute SPARQL queries, which utilize the RDF data produced from the R2RML process.

Fig. 17. SPARQL Endpoint – Common Information Retrieval

Fig.17 further illustrates the practical application of the Unified RDF Specification within the SPARQL endpoint. By deploying the ontologies and vocabularies established in earlier phases, uniform information retrieval across various systems is achieved. For instance, this image captures the retrieval of temperature data as a case study, demonstrating the standardized query's capability to access and collate information regardless of the underlying system-specific fields. The ontology-driven uniformity ensures that data extracted via SPARQL queries is clear, combined, and ready for detailed analysis. The discussion above and the accompanying Figs.13–17 highlight the transformative nature of the proposed method. By utilizing the power of semantic web standards and tools, a transition from a disjointed data landscape to a unified semantic ecosystem is achieved. The success of the approach, demonstrated by the SPARQL endpoint and RDF visualization tools, confirms the capabilities of the methodology.

The practical validation demonstrated some key outcomes, such as the semantic alignment of data from two different systems, enabling integrated queries that provided insights into older adults' activities and environmental conditions. Efficiency was increased by reducing the manual effort required for data integration through automation, replacing the traditionally time-consuming process of manual mapping and model review, and increasing efficacy. The unified semantic model facilitated knowledge retrieval across both systems, allowing users to perform complex queries that combined data from both domains, thereby enhancing the overall usability and understanding of the information.

5 Conclusion

This research demonstrated significant advancements in semantic data integration. The proposed methodology facilitated a unified view of data across various domains and ensured robust interoperability and intelligent data processing. This research demonstrates that the application of the approach in the health-care and IoT sectors has proven effective in managing complex data landscapes, enhancing the accessibility and utility of semantic data models. The integration of RDF and R2RML enabled the seamless alignment of diverse data sources, ensuring that data remains consistent and meaningful across different systems. The results demonstrate the potential of semantic technologies and the practical effectiveness and potential scalability of the proposed approach, which can be instrumental for future deployments and standards in unified data management.

For future work, the methodology aims to be enhanced by exploring the integration of additional domain-specific ontologies, and expanding the approach to include emerging data standards and models. The plan is to refine the automation of the R2RML process, aiming to reduce the need for manual adjustments in the data transformation stage. The intention is to incorporate quantitative evaluation metrics and describe the complexities of this approach to assess the performance improvements and scalability, ensuring its effectiveness and efficiency across various applications. Furthermore, the development of more advanced reasoning capabilities within the RDF store could lead to improved data analysis and knowledge extraction, providing deeper insights and supporting more nuanced decision-making processes.

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